

Sky Coverage and Astrometric Precision for a Hipparcos Recovery Mission

by L Lindegren

1. Introduction

This note gives a mainly graphical presentation of simulation results obtained at Lund Observatory for a Hipparcos recovery mission.

The simulations include a realistic elliptical orbit with period close to 640 min, and interruptions due to:

- station non-visibility, with 1, 2 or 3 stations available;
- Earth and Moon occultations;
- Earth proximity ($h < 10,000$ km); and
- hibernation during extended eclipse periods.

The simulations cover a 2.5 year interval, starting on October 10, 1989, with intermediate outputs after approximately 1, 2, 3, 4, 9, 12, 15, etc months. A set of 5000 test points randomly scattered over the sky was studied rather than the actual Input Catalogue. This is sufficient to follow the evolution of the sky coverage with respect to the determination of the different astrometric parameters, without excessive computing requirements. A corresponding simulation of observations in a geostationary orbit allows simple comparison between the recovery mission and the nominal mission.

Unfortunately the document *Hipparcos Recovery Mission Requirements* by van der Ha and Clausen (1989 Sep 1) reached me only after most of the simulations were already completed. At the time I did not want to delay this study by updating the orbital elements and other parameters according to that document. Also, I do not think that such an update would change the outcome of the present study in any significant way.

2. Orbit

Initial orbit parameters were taken from an ESOC Message (*Hipparcos orbit information* by van der Ha), dated 28.08.89, viz.:

- (a) perigee height 438 km
- (b) orbital period 639.5 min
- (c) inclination 7 deg
- (d) initial ascending node $\Omega = 120$ deg
- (e) initial argument of perigee $\omega = 180$ deg

From (b) one obtains the semi-major axis $a = 24588$ km, which in combination with (a) gives the eccentricity $e = 0.72278$. These were taken as the initial elements at the epoch 1989 Sep 1.0 UT. The initial mean anomaly was set to zero. The orbit was integrated over a three year interval, taking into account perturbations due to the Sun, Moon, and the J_2 term of the Earth's gravity field. The third perturbation is by far the most important, giving rise to a rotation of the line of nodes by $\dot{\Omega} \simeq -0.39$ deg/day and of the perigee by $\dot{\Omega} + \dot{\omega} \simeq +0.38$ deg/day. The evolution of the elements is shown in Figs. 1a-f.

3. Eclipses

From the results of the orbit integration, the duration of every eclipse throughout the three-year period was computed to the nearest minute of time. This is shown in Fig. 2. In the nominal (geostationary) orbit, the maximum eclipse duration would be about 70 min, corresponding to about 5 % of the orbital period. For the recovery mission I assumed that eclipses up to 64 min, or 10 % of the orbit period, could be accepted before the payload would have to be switched off.

This results in two hibernation periods during the interval studied, viz., 1990 Feb 4-Apr 2 and 1991 Sep 12-Oct 14. No observations were assumed to occur during these periods or in the week immediately following each period.

4. Station visibility

The visibility of the satellite from each of three ground stations (Odenwald, Perth and Kourou) was computed at one-minute intervals. The following geocentric positions were assumed:

Station	X [km]	Y [km]	Z [km]
Odenwald	4081.934	644.682	4842.466
Perth	-2368.674	4881.334	-3341.873
Kourou	3855.238	-5049.818	563.081

For all stations a minimum elevation angle of 5 deg was used. The mean visibility obtained for the different stations and combinations of stations are as follows:

ODN	32.0 %
PER	35.9 %
KRU	38.5 %
ODN+PER	61.2 %
ODN+KRU	51.7 %
ODN+PER+KRU	81.0 %

5. Occultations by the Earth and Moon

Intervals of occultations, i.e., when the apparent Earth or Moon is too close to one of the fields of view, were computed as follows. For each minute of time, the field coordinates (w_c, z_c) of the Earth and Moon centres were computed, and similarly the angular radii ρ of the bodies. A sufficient condition for an occultation is of course that $(w_c^2 + z_c^2)^{1/2} < \sin \rho$. If this is not the case, a further computation yields the field coordinates (w_l, z_l) for the point on the limb closest to the field centre. The condition for occultation then reads $(w_l/w_o)^2 + (z_l/z_o)^2 < 1$, where w_o, z_o are the semi-axes of the occultation field. (That

is, an occultation occurs whenever some part of the body is within the occultation field, here assumed to be elliptical and symmetric about the viewing direction.) For the Earth I have taken $w_o = 0.335$ and $z_o = 0.304$, while for the Moon $w_o = 0.127$ and $z_o = 0.096$.

The nominal scanning law was adopted with $\bar{\nu}_0 = 221$ deg and $\Omega_0 = 0$ deg. No attempt was made to synchronize the spin with perigee passages.

Figs. 3a-b show the fraction of each orbital period that is occulted. Averaged over the entire three year interval the fractional dead time caused by the occultations are as follows:

Earth only	9.1 %
Moon only	0.4 %
Earth or Moon	9.5 %

6. Earth proximity

Due to radiation effects it may be necessary to turn off detectors when the altitude of the satellite is below a certain value. A minimum height of 10,000 km was mentioned at the ESOC meeting on August 16. This limit was adopted for the simulations. The corresponding dead time is a nearly constant 14 % of the orbital period.

The combined effect of Earth and Moon occultations and a required minimum height of 10,000 km is shown in Fig. 4. The average dead time due to these effects is 19.9 %.

7. Useful observing time

Potentially useful observing intervals were derived by combining the criteria for no occultation, altitude above 10,000 km, and visibility from at least one ground station. Three cases were considered, in which: (1) only the Odenwald station is available; (2) either Odenwald or Perth can be used; and (3) either Odenwald, Perth or Kourou can be used.

For simplicity, intervals satisfying the above criteria were also considered to be 'useful observing time'. This means that I have neglected some additional dead time due to attitude reacquisitions, intervals of bad RTAD, and data stretches which are simply too short to be of any real value.

[An aside: One should obviously try to make the best use even of very short data stretches (say, a few minutes). With the generally relaxed accuracy requirements of the recovery mission, especially if it lasts only a few months, this may be entirely feasible simply by running the great-circle reductions with postulated instrument parameters (determined, for instance, by interpolation between well-determined reductions). I believe that such partial great circles can very well be used also in the sphere solution to determine the zero points. Thus, very little observing time should be wasted in the form of too-short data stretches.]

Fig. 5 shows the useful observing time (according to this definition), expressed as a fraction of the total time, for the cases of one, two or three ground stations. The averages are:

ODN	28.8 %
ODN+PER	53.8 %
ODN+PER+KRU	69.5 %

8. Sky simulation

Rather than using the actual Input Catalogue, a simulated catalogue of just 5000 'stars', randomly scattered over the sky, was used. This number is sufficient to get reasonable statistics and a good visual impression of sky coverage simply by plotting each star as a dot on a sky map. Fig. 6a shows the distribution of all 5000 stars in an equal area projection of equatorial coordinates (seen from the 'outside' of the sky, with right ascension increasing towards the right and declination upwards). Fig. 6b indicates the ecliptic and the position of the Sun at the beginning of each month. Galactic coordinates in the same projection are outlined in Fig. 6c.

The observability of each star was studied by examining all passages of the two fields of view across the star during an interval of 2.5 years starting on October 10, 1989. If the field crossing ($w = 0$) occurred during an interval of 'useful observing time', as defined in the previous Section, an observation equation of unit weight was added to the normal equations for the five astrometric parameters of the star. Intermediate results were saved after 1, 2, 3, 4 months of observation (after which the first hibernation period begins), and subsequently at approximately quarterly intervals. In this process, the epoch for the positions was gradually shifted so that it always coincides with the mid-time of observations up to the current point of the mission.

A similar set of normal equations was produced for the nominal mission, using a geostationary orbit position at 12 deg West, full station visibility, and identically the same criteria for Earth and Moon occultations. Intermediate results were saved at quarterly intervals up to 2.5 years.

The total output of these simulations consists of 230,000 normal matrices of size 5×5 . Subsequent results were obtained by numerical and statistical analysis of these data.

9. Separability of the astrometric parameters

We know that a complete separation of all five astrometric parameters in general requires a mission lasting about 18 months or more. For a somewhat shorter mission it might be possible to separate the position and the parallax (provided that the proper motion is known *a priori* to sufficient accuracy). For a mission of 6–12 months it is generally thought that only positions can be determined.

For the present study it was necessary to find some automatic criterion by which the separability of the different parameters could be determined. Singular value analysis (SVA) seems to be a natural way to approach this problem. Consequently, the singular values (or eigenvalues) were computed for all the normal equations. The distribution of singular values for the *nominal* mission was then examined as a function of mission length. Based on that examination the following criterion was established and found to give results, for the nominal mission, in good agreement with prior experience:

Let $\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_2 \geq \dots \geq \sigma_5 \geq 0$ be the singular values of the 5×5 normal matrix for a particular star at a particular point in the mission. (The epoch for the position should be centralized, as mentioned in the previous Section.) Then define the 'effective rank' r to be the largest integer such that

$$\sigma_r > A\theta^{r-1}\sigma_1$$

with $A = 0.3$ and $\theta = 0.5$. ($r = 0$ if all singular values are zero, i.e., for zero observations.) The separability of the astrometric parameters can then be inferred from r according to the following rules:

$r = 5$: position, parallax and proper motion are separable;

$r = 3$ or 4 : position and parallax are separable;

$r = 2$: only the position can be determined;

$r \leq 1$: no useful astrometric information.

This criterion was then applied to all normal equations. The results are shown in Figs. 7a-d, giving the fraction of stars with no data, positions only, positions and parallaxes, and all five parameters, as a function of mission length.

Figs. 8a-f shows the sky coverage with respect to positions (i.e., each dot is a star with $r \geq 2$) after 1, 2, 3, 4, 9 and 12 months.

Figs. 9a-c shows the sky coverage with respect to parallaxes ($r \geq 3$) after 4, 9 and 12 months.

Figs. 10a-c shows the sky coverage with respect to proper motions ($r = 5$) after 12, 18 and 24 months.

10. Precision of the astrometric parameters

In order to estimate the precision of the separable parameters, 'coefficients of improvement' relative to a single field of view crossing were computed. These are obtained as the square root of the diagonal elements of the inverted normal equations matrix. However, the full 5×5 matrix was inverted only when $r = 5$; if $r = 3$ or 4 , the 3×3 submatrix corresponding to the position components and the parallax was inverted, while for $r = 2$ only the 2×2 submatrix of the position components was inverted.

For the nominal mission, after 2.5 years, the sky averages for the coefficients were as follows:

Right Ascension (α):	0.147
Declination (δ):	0.122
Parallax:	0.182
Proper motion in α :	0.207
Proper motion in δ :	0.179

Comparison with Table 18.1 in *The Hipparcos Mission*, Vol. III, shows that these coefficients can be translated into mean errors, in milli-arcsec or milli-arcsec/yr, by application of a constant factor, about 8.5 for a 9th magnitude star. In the following I have used, for simplicity, a slightly more conservative factor of 10, in order to convert the coefficients of improvement into milli-arcsec.

The evolution of the resulting formal mean errors is shown in Figs. 11a-d.

These numbers reflect the actually expected astrometric accuracy only in the case when the five astrometric parameters can be separated for the great majority of stars, and then only after a successful sphere solution to determine the zero points of each great circle. This situation would occur roughly after 18 months of the nominal mission, after 2 years of a recovery mission with 2 or 3 ground stations, and after 2.5 years or more in case of a single station.

Earlier than this, one would have to consider also the contributions from less well-determined great circle zero points and, for the cases of $r < 5$, biases in the position and parallax due to the unestimated proper motion.

Concerning the great circle zero points, I believe that these are not a great problem after about 3-4 months of observation, when a sphere solution (for positions only) starts to become feasible. Before that, the zero points would probably have to be determined by

means of FK5 stars and similar in the Input Catalogue. This would probably give zero point errors on the order of 50 milli-arcsec, and hence position errors some factor 5 larger than the formal mean errors, or about 20–25 milli-arcsec.

Concerning biases from the unestimated parameters, the most interesting question is how the *a priori* errors in proper motions would affect the parallaxes in cases when only the position and parallax are solved for (i.e., for $r = 3$). Let $\mathbf{x} = (\Delta\alpha \cos \delta, \Delta\delta, \Delta\Pi)'$ and $\mathbf{y} = (\Delta\mu_\alpha \cos \delta, \Delta\mu_\delta)$ be the two parts of the unknown vector: $\mathbf{x}$ which is estimated, and $\mathbf{y}$ which is assumed to be zero (but in reality is not). Let us similarly partition the full set of observation equations: $\mathbf{Ax} + \mathbf{By} = \mathbf{z}$. The complete normal equations become:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A} & \mathbf{A}'\mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B}'\mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B}'\mathbf{B} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{x} \\ \mathbf{y} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{A}'\mathbf{z} \\ \mathbf{B}'\mathbf{z} \end{pmatrix}$$

from which

$$\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A})^{-1}\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{z} - (\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{A})^{-1}\mathbf{A}'\mathbf{B}\mathbf{y}$$

The second term on the right hand side gives the bias in $\mathbf{x}$ due to the proper motion error $\mathbf{y}$. For the parallax, the bias can be written

$$\Delta\Pi = s_1 \Delta\mu_\alpha \cos \delta + s_2 \Delta\mu_\delta$$

with sensitivity factors s_1 and s_2 that are easily computed from the elements of the normal equations matrix. If the uncertainty in the assumed proper motion is ϵ_μ , then the rms parallax bias is $\epsilon_\mu (s_1^2 + s_2^2)^{1/2}$. This must be added (quadratically) to the formal mean error in parallax. Test calculations show that $(s_1^2 + s_2^2)^{1/2} \simeq 0.2$ for most normals with $r = 3$. Therefore, proper motion errors up to some 10–15 milli-arcsec/yr contribute relatively little to the parallax errors, which in these cases are of the order of 8 milli-arcsec. Most stars taken from the astrometric catalogues have proper motion errors in this range, and these may actually obtain parallaxes (at the 10 milli-arcsec level) after only 4 months of observation.

11. Conclusions

If the mission ends with the first hibernation period in February 1990, i.e., after about 4 months of observation, one would expect to get positions to 5–10 milli-arcsec for some 65 % of the stars in the Input Catalogue (assuming that two ground stations can be used). There are then still two large 'holes' in the sky corresponding to the mean direction to the Sun and the anti-Sun direction (Fig. 8d). Parallaxes to about 10 milli-arcsec may be determined for perhaps 15 % of the stars mainly at high ecliptical latitudes (Fig. 9a).

If the mission can be extended to 9 months, we should get more than 90 % coverage for the positions, and a very sizable number of parallaxes at the 6–8 milli-arcsec level. However, no proper motions can be determined, except by combination with earlier catalogue data.

Fig. 1a-b: Evolution of orbital elements for a 640 min orbit

Fig. 1c-d: Evolution of orbital elements for a 640 min orbit

Fig. 1e-f: Evolution of orbital elements for a 640 min orbit

Fig. 2: Duration of eclipses in the 640 min orbit

Fig. 3a-b: Fraction of each orbital period that is occulted by the Earth (a) and Moon (b).

Fig. 4 (top): Fractional dead time due to occultations (Earth and Moon) and Earth proximity.

Fig. 5 (bottom): Fraction of 'useful observing time' in case of one, two or three ground stations. The curves are running means over 4 days.

Fig. 6a (top): Distribution of 5000 test points ('stars') in an equal-area equatorial projection

Fig. 6b (middle): The ecliptic and the position of the Sun at the beginning of each month in the same projection

Fig. 6c (bottom): Outline of galactic coordinates in the same projection

Fig. 7a (top): The evolution of sky coverage with respect to positions, parallaxes and proper motions in the case of a single ground station

Fig. 7b (bottom): Same as Fig. 7a, but for 2 ground stations

Fig. 7c (top): Same as Fig. 7a, but for 3 ground stations

Fig. 7d (bottom): Same as Fig. 7a, but for the nominal mission (in geostationary orbit)

Fig. 8a: Stars with positions determined after 1 month, in case of 1, 2 and 3 ground stations (top to bottom)

Fig. 8b: Stars with positions determined after 2 months, in case of 1, 2 and 3 ground stations (top to bottom)

Fig. 8c: Stars with positions determined after 3 months, in case of 1, 2 and 3 ground stations (top to bottom)

Fig. 8d: Stars with positions determined after 4 months, in case of 1, 2 and 3 ground stations (top to bottom)

Fig. 8e: Stars with positions determined after 9 months, in case of 1, 2 and 3 ground stations (top to bottom)

Fig. 8f: Stars with positions determined after 12 months, in case of 1, 2 and 3 ground stations (top to bottom)

Fig. 9a: Stars with (positions and) parallaxes determined after 4 months (assuming a priori proper motions available), in case of 1, 2 and 3 ground stations (top to bottom)

Fig. 9b: Stars with (positions and) parallaxes determined after 9 months (assuming a priori proper motions available), in case of 1, 2 and 3 ground stations (top to bottom)

Fig. 9c: Stars with (positions and) parallaxes determined after 12 months (assuming a priori proper motions available), in case of 1, 2 and 3 ground stations (top to bottom)

Fig. 10a: Stars with positions, parallaxes and proper motions determined after 12 months, in case of 1, 2 and 3 ground stations (top to bottom)

Fig. 10b: Stars with positions, parallaxes and proper motions determined after 18 months, in case of 1, 2 and 3 ground stations (top to bottom)

Fig. 10c: Stars with positions, parallaxes and proper motions determined after 24 months, in case of 1, 2 and 3 ground stations

Fig. 11a-b: Evolution of formal mean errors for the positions and parallaxes in case of 1, 2 and 3 ground stations, and for the nominal mission (N). Note that actual errors may be considerably larger, especially for the first half year, as explained in the text.

Fig. 11c: Evolution of formal mean errors for the proper motions in case of 1, 2 and 3 ground stations and for the nominal mission (N).